

FORMATION OF COMPOUNDS OF CUPROUS IODIDE WITH ALKALI AND ALKALINE EARTH METAL IODIDES IN ACETONE

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The double compounds of Cu^I iodide with alkali and alkaline earth metal iodides have been prepared in acetone and their general properties studied.

A large number of complex halides of copper are reported in literature, but according to Remy and Laves (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 571) no complex with more than four halogens is known. Mann, Purdie and Wells (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1503) examined the co-ordination compounds of cuprous iodide with tertiary phosphines and arsines (prepared by shaking phosphine or arsine with an equimolecular quantity of CuI, dissolved in concentrated solution of KI) and concluded that the above derivatives were formed from potassium cupriiodide $K_2[CuI_4]$.

Harris (*J. Proc. Roy. Soc. N.S. Wales*, 1950, III-16, 841) studied the co-ordination compounds of copper formed by treating tetrammine or bis-ethylenediamine copper^{II} halide with appropriate cuprous halide and concluded that these were complex compounds and not physical mixtures. Dutta and Sen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 750) prepared the 2-covalent series iodides $M[CuI_2]$ from a series of organic bases. Wells and Herbert (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1890, 10, 157) obtained colorless crystals corresponding to $(NH_4I)_2 \cdot Cu_2I_2$ or $4NH_4Cl \cdot Cu_2Cl_2$ and $NH_4Cl \cdot 3Cu_2Cl_2$ by cooling the mixtures of a solution of cuprous iodide and ammonium iodide or cuprous chloride and ammonium chloride in presence of HCl and copper wire. Kohn (*Monatsh.*, 1912, 33, 912) prepared a double cuprous iodide with quinoline methiodide, $C_9H_7N \cdot CH_2I \cdot CuI$, by a direct method.

A general survey of literature shows that practically, no work has been done on the formation of double iodides of copper (ous) and alkali and alkaline earth metal iodides in organic solvents. The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the formation of these compounds in acetone.

EXPERIMENTAL

A concentrated solution of a soluble iodide was prepared in a conical flask and cuprous iodide was added to it in small quantities when it dissolved. The process was continued till a small quantity of it was left at the bottom. The mixture was constantly shaken at least for 4 hours, left overnight, and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated on a sand-bath when a crystalline substance was obtained. It was washed several times with acetone, dried in steam-oven and analysed.

Copper was estimated by iodometric method, iodine as AgI, K as perchlorate, Ba and Sr as sulphates, nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method and Ca by precipitating it as calcium oxalate and titrating it against $KMnO_4$. Mg was estimated as $Mg_2P_2O_7$. Lithium and sodium could not be estimated and were found by difference.

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. or Merck's E.P. quality.

TABLE I

Compounds of cuprous iodide with alkali and alkaline earth metal iodides.

No.	Other iodides.	Colour of the compounds isolated.	% Copper.		% Iodine.		% Other metals.		Probable formulae.
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
1	LiI	Brown	19.30	19.59	78.60	78.27	2.10	2.14	Li[CuI ₂]
2	NaI	Light brown	18.73	18.68	74.38	74.56	6.84	6.76	Na[CuI ₂]
3	KI	Brown	17.78	17.83	70.80	71.20	11.42	10.97	K[CuI ₂]
4	NH ₄ I	Dirty brown	18.93	18.95	75.60	75.68	5.47	5.37	NH ₄ [C·I ₂]
5	MgI ₂	Dull white	19.73	19.29	76.45	77.02	3.82	3.69	Mg[₂ CuI ₂]
6	CaI ₂	Reddish brown	18.98	18.84	75.12	75.22	5.90	5.94	Ca[₂ CuI ₂]
7	SrI ₂	"	17.56	17.58	70.22	70.29	12.22	12.13	Sr[₂ CuI ₂]
8	BaI ₂	Brown	16.35	16.46	66.23	65.76	17.42	17.78	Ba[₂ CuI ₂]

Attempts were made to prepare the analogous compounds of CdI₂, Hg₂I₂ and FeI₂, but no compound could be isolated in these cases.

General Properties.—In all these cases slightly coloured and crystalline compounds, fairly stable, if kept out of contact with moist air, were obtained. These are hygroscopic and decompose when left in air for a long time. The compounds obtained with alkaline earth metal iodides are more stable than those obtained with alkali metal iodides, the ammonium compound being most stable. These are fairly soluble in acetone and ammonium hydroxide, sparingly so in alcohol and insoluble in water, benzene and pyridine. On treatment with dilute HNO₃ or HCl, these dissociate into their components, but dissolve in HNO₃ or HCl (conc.).

Cuprous iodide is insoluble in acetone, but its solubility increases in the presence of these iodides which indicates the formation of complex compounds. An examination of the table shows that one molecule of an alkali metal iodide combines with one molecule of cuprous iodide, but one molecule of alkaline earth metal iodide combines with two molecules of CuI; the compounds formed may be represented as M[CuI₂] and M[₂CuI₂]. All these compounds are unstable and decompose when heated above 150° or boiled with water. This seems to be due to the fact that the E.A.N. of copper in these compounds is 32, and therefore these do not possess a stable configuration.

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